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A STUDY ON OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG THE TEXTILE MANAGERS IN TIRUPUR

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Abstract

This research was conducted to investigate the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among textile managers. This paper aims to find out the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction based on age, gender, marital status, work experience and income of textile managers in Tirupur. 553 Textile managers were invited to participate in the questionnaire survey. A cross sectional study was used to examine the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction. Descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis were employed to analyse the data. The findings also revealed that there is a significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction.

Key Words: Occupational Stress, Job satisfaction, Demographics, Textile industry

Introduction:-

Stress in the workplace is a growing concern in the current state of the economy, where employees increasingly face conditions of overwork, job insecurity, low levels of job satisfaction and lack of autonomy. Workplace stress has been shown to have a detrimental effect on the health and wellbeing of employees, as well as a negative impact on workplace productivity and profits. There are measures that individuals and organizations can take to alleviate the negative impact of stress, or to stop it from arising in the first place. However, employees first need to learn to recognize the signs that indicate they are feeling stressed out, and employers need to be aware of the effects that stress has on their health as well as on company profits. This report is a call to employers to take action on stress levels in the workplace.

Occupational stress has become one of the most serious health issues in the modern world (Lu et al., 2003). Occupational stress has become one of the most popular topics for applied research in psychology, and in the broader areas of social and medical sciences. Occupational stress, also known as job stress, has been defined as the experience of negative emotional states such as frustration, worry, anxiety and depression attributed to work related factors (Kyriacou, 2001). Occupational stress is also defined as the perception of a discrepancy between environmental demands (stressors) and individual capacities to fulfill these demands (Topper, 2007). Occupational stress, in particular, is the inability to cope with the pressures in a job, because of a poor fit between someone's abilities and his/her work requirements and conditions (Holmlund-Rytkönen and Strandvik, 2005).

Several studies have shown that occupational stress can lead to various negative consequences for the individual and the workplace (Oginska-Bulik, 2006). Extreme stress can lead to decreased productivity and an overall negative impact on the organization itself. People with a higher percentage of occupational stress may not be satisfied with their job and therefore they will not feel happy working in the organization. Therefore, it is very important for employer and employees to realize the stress and the stressor that cause all the negative effects (Bhatti et al., 2011). This study aims to investigate the relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among managerial personnel and to identify the factor that influence employees job satisfaction. This study will assist the employees to identify their occupational stress and give good implications towards their job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job, which acts as a motivation to work. It is not the self-satisfaction, happiness or self- contentment, but the satisfaction on the job.

For almost all organizations, employees are the vital resource and they represent an important asset of an industry. Human resource management is concerned with developing potential, of employees so that they get maximum job satisfaction from their work and give their best efforts to the organisation. The workers in a job are not machines, but contributors to production. The happier people are within their job, the more satisfied they are said to be. Thus, job satisfaction describes how content an individual is with his or her job. It is not the same as motivation. It is job design which enhances job satisfaction and performance. The other influences on satisfaction are the management style and culture, employee involvement, empowerment and autonomous work groups. Job satisfaction is a very important attribute which is frequently measured by organizations.

Review of Literature:

Chan et.al. (2000) examined work stress among professionals and para-professions (namely general practitioners, lawyers, engineers, teachers, nurses and life insurance personnel) in Singapore. Results showed that performance pressure and work family conflict were perceived to be the most stressful aspects of work. These two stressors also significantly contributed to the experience of overall work stress.

Spector et. al. (2000) examined a longitudinal study that even after controlling for NA and prior levels of strains, relations would still be found between job stressors and job strains. In this, negative affectivity (NA) and strains were assessed both in college and later on the job. Stressors were assessed only on the job. Evidence was found that some background factors affected measures of job stressors and job strains. The observed relations between job stressors and job strains could not be attributable to third variable that might affect these specific strains. Relations between job stressors and job strains, however, were in most cases not affected significantly when prior strains and NA were controlled for. Furthermore, the results suggested that NA measures are subject to occasion factors.

Shah (2003) examined role stress among employees in banking industry. The results indicated that most of the employees were experiencing moderate level of stress at work. It revealed that role stagnation, inadequacy of role authority, role erosion and role overload were the main stressors being encountered by employees.

Ashok Pratap Singh and Ashish Kumar Dubey (2011), at Banaras Hindu University, conducted a study on 210 managers from different private sector organizations to examine the role of stress (role stress) and locus of control on job satisfaction. For measurement of role stress, Occupational Stress Index (Srivastava and Singh, 1981) was used; for measurement of locus of control, Social Reaction Inventory (Rotter, 1966) was used; and for measurement of job satisfaction, S-D Employees' Inventory (Pestonjee, 1979) was used. The results of correlation indicated that role overload was significantly negatively correlated to satisfaction with management and total satisfaction; role ambiguity was significantly negatively correlated to satisfaction with management; and role conflict was significantly negatively correlated to satisfaction with management and total satisfaction. Overall stress was significantly negatively correlated to satisfaction with management and total satisfaction. The results of step-wise

multiple regression analysis showed that total stress contributed 7.4% variance in explaining satisfaction with management, and role conflict contributed 7.1% variance in explaining total satisfaction.

Nural Ain Bt Syed Alwee (2012) examined the relationship between occupational stress, job satisfaction, and intent to leave towards organisational commitment. A convenience sample group of 130 employees of North Port (Malaysia) were selected over 2272 of total population at year 2009. A self-administrated survey instrument was developed to measure and test the employee's external environment occupational stress, job satisfaction, and intent to leave towards organisational commitment. Using SPSS 16.0 two statistical tests were employed to test study hypotheses. First by measuring correlation a Pearson correlation coefficient analysis was used to identify the relationship between predictor and criterion variables. Likewise multiple regressions were used to determine the effect between external environment, occupational stress and job satisfaction among related variables. The findings revealed that job satisfaction, occupational stress and intent to leave do affect organisational commitment. At the same time the occupational stress gives to the intent to leave.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the level of occupational stress among the managerial personnel of Textile industry in Tirupur.
2. To find out the level of job satisfaction among the managerial personnel of Textile industry in Tirupur.
3. To study the impact of occupational stress on job satisfaction among the managerial personnel of Textile industry in Tirupur.
4. To analyze the effect of various demographic variables such as age, gender, education, experience, marital status, income on occupational stress, coping strategies, and job satisfaction among the managerial personnel of Textile industry.

METHODOLOGY

A convenience sample consisting of ninety employees working in selected textile mills participated in the study. Questionnaires were administered to assess occupational stress and job satisfaction. The collected data was analysed with Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA, and Correlation.

Instruments:

Occupational Stress Scale

Fifteen items were selected from the Occupational Stress Index developed by Srivastava and Singh (1981). These items relate to role overload, role ambiguity, and role conflict. The respondents were asked to rate each of the 15 items on the following 5-point Likert scale: Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly disagree

Responses were scored as follows:

Strongly agree = 5, agree=4, neutral=3, disagree=2, strongly disagree=1

Job satisfaction Scale

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Short Form) was used to assess job satisfaction among the managerial personnel. The respondents were asked to rate each of the 20 items on the following 5-point Likert scale: Very satisfied, Satisfied, Neutral, Dissatisfied, Very dissatisfied

Responses were scored as follows:

Very satisfied = 5, Satisfied =4, Neutral =3, Dissatisfied =2, Very dissatisfied =1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the analysis of the data collected from the respondents.

Table: 1 Demographic characteristics of the Sample

S.No	Demographic Variables	Group	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
1	Age (in years)	30 & Below	144	26.0
		31 – 45	233	42.2
		Above 45	176	31.8
2	Gender	Male	367	66.4
		Female	186	33.6
3	Marital Status	Married	304	55.0
		Unmarried	249	45.0
4	Educational Qualification	Diploma	149	26.9
		Undergraduate	234	42.4
		Postgraduate	170	30.7
5	Work Experience (in years)	Below 5	129	23.4
		5 – 10	270	48.8
		Above 10	154	27.8
6	Monthly Income (in rupees)	Below 20000	200	36.2
		20000-30000	269	48.6
		Above 30000	84	15.2
	Total		553	100

Source: Primary Data

The demographic profile of the respondents in the study showed that out of the total 553 respondents taken for the study, 42.2 percentage of the respondents belong to the age group of 31 – 40 years; 66.4 percentage of the respondents are male; 55 percentage of the respondents are married; 42.4 percentage of the respondents are undergraduate; 48.8 percentage of the respondents belong to 5 -10 years of work experience; 48.6 percentage of the respondents belong to the income group of 20000 – 30000 rupees.

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS

Null hypothesis:

H1- Occupational stress will not vary significantly with variation in demographic factors like age (H1a), gender (H1b), education (H1c), experience (H1d), marital status (H1e), and monthly income (H1f) among the managerial personnel of Textile industry.

Table 2 Occupational Stress among different age groups

Age	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	F-value
30 & Below	55.48	144	4.840	12.953 (.000)
31 – 45	57.65	233	3.660	
Above 45	57.11	176	3.886	
Total	56.91	553	4.155	

Source: Primary Data

The table 3.2 shows that the overall mean score for occupational stress ranges from 55.48 to 57.65. The 31 - 45 age group had a higher mean score (57.65) for occupational stress than the other age groups. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in occupational stress among different age groups. The obtained F-value is 12.953 and it is significant at 1% level. Hence, hypothesis H1a was rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in occupational stress among different age groups.

Table 3 Occupational Stress among different Gender groups

Gender	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	t-value
Male	56.99	367	4.047	3.370 (0.067)
Female	56.76	186	4.367	
Total	56.91	553	4.155	

Source: Primary Data

The table 3.3 shows that the overall mean score for occupational stress ranges from 56.76 to 56.99. The male respondents had a higher mean score (56.99) for occupational stress than the female respondents (56.76). Independent sample t-test was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in occupational stress among different gender groups. The obtained t-value is 3.370 and it is not significant. Hence, hypothesis H1b was accepted and it was concluded that there is no statistically significant difference in occupational stress among different gender groups.

Table:4 Occupational Stress among different marital Status groups

Marital Status	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	t-value
Married	57.58	304	3.592	18.057 (0.000)
Unmarried	56.10	249	4.632	
Total	56.91	553	4.155	

Source: Primary Data

The table 3.4 shows that the overall mean score for occupational stress ranges from 56.10 to 57.58. The married respondents had a higher mean score (57.58) for occupational stress than the unmarried respondents (56.10). Independent sample t-test was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in occupational stress among different marital groups. The obtained t-value is 18.057 and it is significant at 1% level. Hence, hypothesis H1e was rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in occupational stress among different marital groups.

Table: 5 Occupational Stress among different education groups

Education Qualification	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	F-value
Diploma	57.03	149	3.930	0.090 (0.914)
Undergraduate	56.84	234	4.429	
Postgraduate	56.91	170	3.974	
Total	56.91	553	4.155	

Source: Primary Data

The table 3.5 shows that the overall mean score for occupational stress ranges from 56.84 to 57.03. The Diploma respondents had a higher mean score (57.03) for occupational stress than the other groups. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in occupational stress among different education groups. The obtained F-value is .090 and it is not significant. Hence, hypothesis H1c was accepted and it was concluded that there is no statistically significant difference in occupational stress among different education groups.

Table 6 Occupational Stress among different experience groups

Work Experience	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	F-value
Below 5	57.05	129	4.146	0.353
5 – 10	56.76	270	4.379	
Above 10	57.06	154	3.754	
Total	56.91	553	4.155	

Source: Primary Data

The table 3.6 shows that the overall mean score for occupational stress ranges from 56.76 to 57.06. The above 10 year experience group had a higher mean score (57.06) for occupational stress than the other experience groups. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in occupational stress among different education groups. The obtained F-value is 0.353 and it is not significant. Hence, hypothesis H1d was accepted and it was concluded that there is no statistically significant difference in occupational stress among different experience groups.

Table 7 Occupational Stress among different income groups

Monthly Income	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	F-value
Below 20000	57.03	200	4.195	7.414 (0.001)
20000-30000	56.38	269	4.199	
Above 30000	58.33	84	3.558	
Total	56.91	553	4.155	

Source: Primary Data

The table 3.7 shows that the overall mean score for occupational stress ranges from 56.38 to 58.33. The above 30000 income group had a higher mean score (58.33) for occupational stress than the other income groups. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in occupational stress among different income groups. The obtained F-value is 7.414 and it is significant at 1% level. Hence, hypothesis H1f was rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in occupational stress among different income groups.

JOB SATISFACTION

Null Hypothesis:

H3- Job satisfaction will not vary significantly with variation in demographic factors like age (H3a), gender (H3b), education (H3c), experience (H3d), marital status (H3e), and monthly income (H3f) among the managerial personnel of Textile Industry.

Table 8 Job satisfaction among different age groups

Age	Mean	N	Std.Deviation	F-value
30 & Below	68.46	144	8.446	36.607 (.000)
31 – 45	61.78	233	6.531	
Above 45	63.35	176	7.787	
Total	64.02	553	7.939	

Source : Primary Data

The table 3.14 shows that the overall mean score for job satisfaction ranges from 61.78 to 68.46. The 30 & below age group had a higher mean score (68.46) for job satisfaction than the 31 - 45 age group (61.78). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in job satisfactions among different age groups. The obtained F-value is 36.607 and it is significant at 1% level. Hence, hypothesis H3a was rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in job satisfaction among different age groups.

Table 9 Job satisfaction among different gender groups

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	F-value
Male	63.85	367	7.808	6.957 (.009)
Female	64.34	186	8.203	
Total	64.02	553	7.939	

Source : Primary Data

The 3.15 table shows that the overall mean score for job satisfaction ranges from 63.85 to 64.34. The female gender group had a higher mean score (64.34) for job satisfaction than the male gender group (63.85). Independent sample t-test was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in job satisfactions among different gender groups. The obtained t-value is 6.957 and it is significant. Hence, hypothesis H3b was rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in job satisfaction among different gender groups.

Table 10 Job satisfaction among different marital status groups

Marital	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Married	62.19	304	6.426	80.753 (.000)
Unmarried	66.25	249	8.985	
Total	64.02	553	7.939	

Source : Primary Data

The table 3.16 shows that the overall mean score for job satisfaction ranges from 62.19 to 66.25. The unmarried marital group had a higher mean score (66.25) for job satisfaction than the married marital group (62.19). Independent sample t-test was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in job satisfactions among different marital groups. The obtained t-value is 80.753 and it is significant at 1% level. Hence, hypothesis H3e was

rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in job satisfaction among different marital groups.

Table 11 Job satisfaction among different education groups

Education	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	F-value
Diploma	64.23	149	7.715	0.711 (.341)
Undergraduate	64.18	234	8.741	
Postgraduate	63.60	170	6.940	
Total	64.02	553	7.939	

Source : Primary Data

The table 3.17 shows that the overall mean score for job satisfaction ranges from 63.60 to 64.23. The diploma respondents had a higher mean score (64.23) for job satisfaction than the post graduate respondents (63.60). ANOVA was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in job satisfactions among different education groups. The obtained F-value is -0.341 and it is not significant. Hence, hypothesis H3c was accepted and it was concluded that there is no statistically significant difference in job satisfaction among different education groups.

Table 12 Job satisfaction among different experience groups

Experience	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	F-value
Below 5	62.91	129	8.614	5.725 (.003)
5 – 10	65.18	270	7.959	
Above 10	62.91	154	7.022	
Total	64.02	553	7.939	

Source : Primary Data

The table 3.18 shows that the overall mean score for job satisfaction ranges from 62.91 to 65.18. The above 5 - 10 years experience group had a higher mean score (65.18) for job satisfaction than other experience groups. ANOVA was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in job satisfaction among different experience groups. The obtained F-value is 5.725 and it is significant at 1% level. Hence, hypothesis H3d was rejected and it was concluded that there is a statistically significant difference in job satisfaction among different experience groups.

Table 13 Job satisfaction among different income groups

Income	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	F-value
Below 20000	64.08	200	8.393	0.808 (0.214)
20000-30000	64.14	269	8.306	
Above 30000	63.50	84	5.219	
Total	64.02	553	7.939	

Source : Primary Data

The table 3.19 shows that the overall mean score for job satisfaction ranges from 63.50 to 64.14 among different income groups. The 20000 - 30000 income group had a higher mean score (64.14) for job satisfaction than other income groups. ANOVA was applied to ascertain if there was a significant difference in job satisfactions among different income groups. The obtained F-value is 0.214 and it is not significant. Hence, hypothesis H3f was accepted and it was concluded that there is no statistically significant difference in job satisfaction among different income groups.

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND JOB SATISFACTION

Null hypothesis:

H4- There will not be any significant correlation between job satisfaction and occupational stress (H4a);

Table 14. Correlation among stress and job satisfaction

		Stress	Job Satisfaction
Stress	Pearson Correlation	1	-.497**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N		553

Correlation test revealed that there was significant correlation ($r=-.497$ & $p<.01$) between stress and job satisfaction. Hence hypothesis H4a was rejected.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS WITH OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AS PREDICTOR VARIABLE AND JOB SATISFACTION AS THE DEPENDENT VARIABLE.

Null hypothesis:

H5- Occupational stress (H5) will not affect job satisfaction among the managerial personnel of Textile industry.

Table 15 Regression analysis with occupational stress as predictor variable and job satisfaction as the dependent variable.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.497 ^a	.247	.246	6.895

a. Predictors: (Constant), Stress

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8595.603	1	8595.603	180.782	.000 ^a
	Residual	26198.216	551	47.547		
	Total	34793.819	552			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Stress

b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	118.071	4.031		29.292	.000
	Stress	-.950	.071	-.497	-13.446	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Regression analysis was conducted to investigate the relationship between stress and job satisfaction. F-Test was statistically significant, which means that the model was statistically significant. The R-Squared is 0.246 which means that approximately 24% of the variance of job satisfaction was explained by the predictor variable, that is, stress. Hence hypothesis H5a was rejected.

CONCLUSION

Textile sector in India is facing so many problems. The problem of stress is inevitable and unavoidable in the Textile sector. A majority of the workforce face severe occupational stress and a lot of psychological problems. The productivity of the work force is the most crucial factor as far as the success of an organization is concerned. The productivity in turn is dependent on the satisfaction of the employees. The innovative behavior of employees is also important especially in service organizations. The present study was carried out with an objective of explaining the relationship between the occupational stress and job satisfaction. The researcher also scrutinized the available literature with respect to occupational stress and its impact on job satisfaction to conceptualize the frame work of the study. The findings of the study confirmed that stress affects the satisfaction level of the employees.

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